

The Influencing Factors of Marketing Mix Strategies That Affect the Sustainability of Business Performance: the Case of Ethiopian Commodity Exchange

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Abstract – The study aim focused on the dimensions of marketing mixes strategies on Sustainable Business Performance: a case of Ethiopian Commodity Exchange. The research philosophy of research Paradigms has designed Quantitative and Deductive research approach and researchers have used an Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) research design and the researchers are using the Stratified sampling techniques and simple random sampling techniques, method of data collectection from Suppliers, Primary Cooperative, Secondary Cooperative and Employee of Ethiopian Commodity Exchange, traders data analyzed using SPSS software (Version 22), the researchers can be used both primary the Secondary data collection, through questionnaires and secondary data to prepare the research collected from the source of various document of the Ethiopia Commodity Exchange. At the end the researcher can concluded, and data analyzed to describe from the Exploratory factor analyze, based on Correlation matrix, KMO, Average Variance Extracted, Factor Loading and Rotation Matrix analyze, Scatter plot and to construct the internal consistence of Convergent validity and reliably test alpha result of Composite reliability the information that collected from primary and secondary source.

Keywords: Marketing Mix Strategies, Business Performance, Product strategies, price Strategies, promotional Strategies and place Strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

(Nagle, Holden S., 2016), To achieve a set of organizational goals and objectives, companies conceptualize, design, and implementation of various strategies can be business corporate, business or Marketing strategies constitute one of the functional market strategies amenable to application by contemporary companies in order to enhance performance, and Marketing has been defined and conceptualized in various way depend on the author's back ground, interest and marketing strategy education

In today's highly marketing competitive business environment every organization whether profit oriented or not has its own mission to achieve for organizations to meet their goals. Their first focus is to fulfill their customers need and market expectations. Business market Orientation Strategic thinking represents a new market development perspective in the area of marketing. Marketing orientation plays a vital role in the strategic management process of a business firm, and the experience of companies well versed in strategic planning indicates that failure in marketing can block the way to goals established by the strategic plan, within a given business environment, marketing mix strategies that deals essentially with the interplay of three forces "C" known as the strategic customer, the competition, and the corporation. Marketing strategies focus on ways in which the corporation can differentiate itself effectively from its competitors, capitalizing on its distinctive strengths to deliver better value to its customers as posited by (N., Falk, 2017).

(Alemayehu Amano N., 2018), when an organization is ready to embrace sustainability of Business Performance of marketing mix strategies that becomes the issue of critical and the issues like planned obsolescence, unsustainable packaging, and fast fashion are direct effects of marketing strategies solely centered on capitalism and business profit, and a proven strategy that marketers can tap into is the use of nudges, or subtle behavioral cues and the researchers found that hotel restaurants using “simple and non-intrusive ‘nudges’” like reducing plate size and posting signs about waste, it reduced the amount of food waste by around 20% and there is a business rising interest in behavioral insights and there are nudge units popping up around the globe, said and by creating strategies that reduce waste and operational costs, marketers can help create a win-win situation for businesses and consumers while still embracing sustainability (Dr. Habit, 2020).

(Alemayehu Amano N., 2018), The Ethiopian Commodity Exchange has gifted with the environment sustainable for producing high quality Different Commodity like Coffee, Horicon Bean, Maze, Burley and Other Commodities, that despite this, Ethiopian Commodity industry has been suffering from a number of multifaceted limitations. The problems relate to marketing production, business commodity processing and sustainable marketing. In terms of production, Ethiopian Commodity Exchange that remains to be low yield due to, among others, lack of advanced technology, lack or shortage of cultivators suitable for different localities. In relation to processing, the main interest at stake is the Different Bean quality Commodities plays irreplaceable role in the increasingly competitive international different market. In Ethiopia, however, the quality of large quantity of coffee is believed to decline as result of poor and traditional techniques.

Due to this, to develop new marketing tools, new business concepts, new business strategy and the new mindsets to cope with the turbulent and chaotic environments leading to discontinuous change. Ethiopian Commodity Exchange has faced with some problems while practicing and implementing the marketing mix strategy with respect to organizations’ profitability. World price of coffee affects coffee export positively its export price elasticity was 2.48, while the impact of producer and export price is insignificant in the long run as well as in the short run. The estimated elasticity for domestic supply of coffee, exchange rate and GDP were 1.07, .891 and 1.35 respectively, (MOT, 2015).

However, those researchers did not mention this in detail about what the strategies can affect specifically to the Marketing Mix Strategies among countries, it perhaps especially in Ethiopia. So, this is the reason why this study aimed and the Ethiopian Commodity Exchange that actively implemented in Ethiopian Commodity Commercialization, the system that to sustain and upgrade like a system of coffee of Maize, Haricot bean, Dairy, Oilseeds and pulse for tried to examine on what and how the Marketing Mix Strategies Affected marketing mix strategies (Product, Pricing, Promotion and Place/ Distribution) on sustainable Business Performance has not only Coffee to fully implemented in this organization and additionally, the overall success has depending on the knowledge of what factors constrain Marketing Mix Strategies and sustainable Business Performance on the economic growth of the country.

These marketing mix strategies gaps that caught the attention of the researcher to do study has the different Commodity, and that the sustainability of business economic growth relation in the context of Ethiopia, in turn on how it affects the Organizational Profitability in Ethiopian Commodity Exchange, and determine its influence level.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To analyses the extent to which product strategy influences on Sustainable Business Performance.

- To examine the extent to which pricing strategy relationship on Sustainable Business Performance.
- To investigate the extent to which promotion strategy effects on Sustainable Business Performance.
- To scrutinize the extent to which place/distribution strategy influences on Sustainable Business Performance.

3. MARKETING MIX STRATEGIES

The Marketing Mixes strategies, and the marketing mixes actions that can take a business, to sell the products or services that can take, and make the contribution of their turnover of every business, and any exchange of the commodity exchange of the business of small, or big organization, to understand an important write marketing mix strategies which can help them in the sale of any items they make or sell the business commodity organizations, and the strategy is an underlying concept in strategic business management. However, the marketing mix strategies is a set of controllable practice n ECX, or the tactical tools in marketing mix research which are used by an organization so as to meet the needs business activities and marketing mix strategies demands in the target market, (Annemarie Halon , 2022).

4. THE INFLUENCING FACTORS OF MARKETING MIX STRATEGIES AND SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS PERFORMANCE

Product Strategies

(Ayasar, Kanza, 2022), the product that has what it selling, whether its physical goods, or intangible services, when you think about the product, you should be also considering the experiences that can users have in the capacity of production, and to test better packaging, and to attract a people with the quality of product and services Marketers strategies as a broadly new production to the innovations, product scope, and the manufacturing raw materials, and it represents an item or service designed to satisfy customer needs and wants, and effectively market a product or service, it's important to identify what differentiates it from competing products or services. It's also important to determine if other products or services can be marketed in conjunction with sustainable Business Performance.

Pricing Strategies

(Tellis, G. , 214), the price product of each strategies is what it costs, and the sellers want to change as much as possible, and the buyers want to pay, as little as possible, and it compromise somewhere in the middle, between what seller want, and what buyer want, to the sale price of the product reflects what the consumers are willing, to pay for it and the Marketing professionals to need to consider costs related to research and development, manufacturing, marketing, and distribution otherwise known as cost-based pricing. Pricing based primarily on consumers' perceived quality or value is known as value-based pricing, (Joseph L. Rodman, 2022).

Promotional Strategies

(Brassington N. O, 2015), Promotional Strategies of the Joint marketing campaigns that the best product, and perfect price alone the promotional strategies that can covers all the communications tactic and that you use to tell people about product, and services and it includes the promotional that translate themselves and the audience of the message are addressed and messages also are a promotional mix. Activities might include advertising, sales promotion, personal selling, and public relations. A key consideration should be for the budget assigned to the marketing mix and the marketing professionals that carefully construct a

message that often incorporates details from the other three Ps when trying to reach their target audience. Determination of the best mediums to communicate the message and decisions about the frequency of the communication also are important.

Place Strategies

The Place and the distribution of where, the channel of the production that can be buyers and find the product to sustain his strategy and on the area of marketing perspectives it will be distributing, the product and services, whether that a brick-and-mortar location, or an online shops that can be a thoughtful thinking, and that the ideal distribution system, as well as final distribution, that can also need to considering, the good place to begin the good strategic distribution of the organization, than the customer and consumer what that trying to sell, retail stories of online market and direct selling from consumers and whole selling of the business organization,(Lesener 2019);.

Sustainable Performance

(Nagle a& Holden, 2016), In today's profit driven world, marketers are often charged with achieving very ambitious targets, and having been a marketer that are found himself sucked into the world of Business Performance, and Organizational profit that other profit in other word, and the profitability centric nature of traditional marketing system, that are reinforced by the rewards marketers get for hitting specific targets and business Performance awareness spreads, and the profitability of business marketers are the beginning to the traditional form of marketing system to sustain, and move forward, and the Marketing mixes strategies that can be mattered, because it is very much intertwined with business for the sustainability of business profitability that can run of marketing advantage from Manual to technological marketing Commodity systems, and Sustainable Marketing mixes strategies is present in every stage of a business organization.

5. EXPLORING ETHIOPIAN COMMODITY EXCHANGE

In 2007, The Economist Eleni Gabre-Mahin appeared in a famous where she outlined her ambitious vision to found the first commodities market in Ethiopia. Her plan, she said, would create wealth, minimize risk for farmers and turn one of the world's poorest countries into one of its fastest growing economies, and it became new market development to be spread highly in Ethiopian Commodity Exchange in 2008, helping to launch the only functioning commodity exchange in Africa at the time.

Today, another African countries that also operate commodity exchanges, but the Ethiopian exchange was the first of its kind. It has largely been considered to have successfully modernized the country's economy, linked smallholder farmers to markets, and enhanced food security, and

ECX is a partnership between market actors, the members of the exchange, and the Government of Ethiopia. Its mission is to "bring integrity, security, and efficiency to the market, creating opportunities for unparalleled growth in the commodity sector to launch different Category of New product development to sustain spread in Ethiopia, (Perfect Daily Grind, 2022).

Investigation Gap

Usually, following revising diverse publications, it has noted that (Lubbadeh, 2021), The over the many research journal and investigation credentials have the many problems gap in statement of the problem and problem statement to derive time, (Lesener 2019); challenge in the process of Marketing Mix Strategies and unravel to investigate in Ethiopian Commodity Exchange has to fill the problem gaps of the research of the reeseach predicted association to investigation each predicator in the worth research parameters of

technique logical vacuum of theoretical and empirical gap with citation problem and copy pasts in many research paradigms (Strah & Rupp, 2020); like Investigation research approach qualitative, quantitative, and Mixed research design to confirm build the model, Information analyze and Interpretation based on the output of data (Pereira et. al., 2021), Sampling technique strategy for population category of homogeneity and heterogeneity was face challenge to give good reason for sample size determination for large data sample size fill small sample size in study time, deficit of methodological philosophy gap based on the theory or research approach, and to analyze and interpreted each problem, (Guthier et. al., 2020; Halcomb wt. al., 2018). Deficit of Information Source, and Collection Techniques, deficit of data analyze and interpreting ability and finally, defecating factors that affect influencing Marketing Mix strategies and Sustainable Business Performance and the process Exploratory factor analyze (EFA) predicator investigation not fit Thus, investigation of Marketing Mix strategies has put forward to solve these research gaps (Waithanji& Wakaba, 2014). Thus, study will have solved the problem of the Marketing Mix strategies to rise to fill these gaps.

6. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual framework

Fig -1: AMOS Developed Conceptual framework (2022)

Investigation Technology

Based on the research purpose the study, most commonly used the research philosophy of research Paradigms has designed Quantitative and Deductive research approach, the data analyses designed with Exploratory factor analysis (EFA), to be used for the cases of statistical conclusion to collect actionable insights of essential and number provide the better perspective for making and to draw from complex numerical data and analyze to prove by SPSS software to analysis by Exploratory factor analysis (EFA),to analysis Correlation Matrix of Significant P-Value tested, KMO, Communalities, Average variance Extracted, Rotated Component Matrix, Scree plot component number, Component rotated space and to test Convergent construct validity and Discriminant Reliability to test Cronbach alpha of Exploratory Factor

Analyze for statistical data that can be attempts to identify the and to be constructed, and that can parsimoniously explain the covariance that observed among a set of the measurement model that are directly influenced Indigenous variable in the scores attained by those people on the measurement value of variables that can be described by, (Brown, 2015).

Sampling Technique

Simple random sample each member of population has an equal chance of assortment. It ways that each Coffee suppliers, Primary Cooperative Union, Secondary Cooperative Union, Employee of ECX, Coffee Marketing traders from the ECX of Addis Abebe, Awassa, Dire Dawa and Bule Hora ECX has the chance be selected, and the Stratified random sample of the population is divided into mutually exclusive groups (such as age groups) and random samples are drawn from each group (Yaqub, M., Sohil, F., Shabir, J., 2015). So, the Scholar was use the stratified sampling techniques in order to divide the total population into Coffee suppliers, Primary Cooperative Union, Secondary Cooperative Union, Employee of ECX, and Coffee Marketing traders are participated.

Sample Size

The degree of precision desired, objective(s) of research by taking these factors in to consideration, the researcher was employed, According to Woredas (2019) annual report, does the Cooperative Members have a total of 5 different ware houses, which is found in West Guji Zone Kercha woreda, in Ethiopia. However, the study purposively selects from Cooperative union's members are selected 177, from Coffee supplier 85 respondents are selected, from Woreda Coffee Natural Recourse Officer was 10 respondents selected totally 212 respondents are selected. Additionally, Coffee Natural Recourse was taken as participants in the study, Benouahmane, B., Annie, C., & Yaman, I. , 2019) as follows:

$$\frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{3583}{1 + 3583(0.05)^2} = 360$$

The table shows that the coefficient for the procurement enablers and engagement of worker related predictors, Product Strategy, Price Strategy, Promotion Strategy, Pace Strategy (.870, .818, .879 & .910) respectively, and Sustainable Organizational Profitability .925. Therefore, the overall reliability test indicated that good reliability and internal consistency for which is greater than the benchmark value (i.e., >.70).

7. EXPLORATORY PREDICATOR INVESTIGATION

Marketing Mix Strategies significant level

Fig -2: Marketing Mix Strategies significant level

Source: AMOS Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) Output (2022)

Table -1: Correlation Matrix

Table 1. Correlation matrix of Predicator investigation						
		Product Strategies	Price Strategies	Promotional Strategy	Place Strategies	Organizational Profitability
Correlation	Product Strategies	1.000	.554	.459	.554	.580
	Price Strategies	.580	1.000	.578	.580	.700
	Promotion Strategies	.700	.580	1.000	.534	.668
	Place Strategies	.668	.580	.534	1.000	.750
	Business Performance	.750	.700	.668	.750	1.000
a. Determinant = .076						

Source: Correlation Matrix output, 2022

Correlation matrix table that display the correlation coefficients for different variables that depicts correlation between all the possible pairs of value, it is a powerful tools to summarize large data set to identify all visualize pattern in data set, it can be seen at all the variables are positively correlated necessitating the

significance arrow 1 diagonal number is more than 0.3 the variables after delated correlation Value of Product Strategy.680, Price Strategy.702, Place Strategy.668 Place Strategy .790 in the field of correlation coefficient as justified for the use of Exploratory factor analyzing hypotheses tests to be acceptable and positive significant correlation matrix in this study.

Table -2: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

KMO and Bartlett’s Test Factor analysis		
Table 2. KMO and Bartlett’s Test		
Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.844
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi–Square	2405.541
	df	153
	Sig.	.000

Source: KMO and Bartlett's Test 2022

Predicator investigation is appropriate for this information and the sphericity calculates (Bartlett test) the potential of the association among enablers and as of these information, the test of Bartlett is considerable .844, which is associated as Chi-Square 2405.541Degree of freedom 153 probabilities is less than 0.05. Test of Bartlett for information is .000 and this shows the significance maximum fit well to the predicator investigation.

Communalities

Table -3: Communalities Calculate of Variance Enabler

	Initial	Extraction
PROD1	1.000	.688
PROD2	1.000	.725
PROD3	1.000	.608
PRIC1	1.000	.571
PRIC2	1.000	.673
PRIC3	1.000	.561
PROM1	1.000	.673
PROM2	1.000	.640

PROD1			.743		
PROD2			.802		
PROD3			.581		
PRIC1		.658			
PRIC2		.639			
PRIC3		.735			
PROM1				.717	
PROM2				.783	
PROM3				.719	
PLAC1	.831				
PLAC2	.723				
PLAC3	.693				
PLAC4	.753				
SMP 1					.712
SMP 2					.764
SMP 3					.751
SMP 4					.634
SMP 5					.639

Source: Principal Component Analysis of Factor Loading 2022

Item of Component 1 Place Strategies correlated each other, Item of Component 2 Correlated with Price Strategies, Item of Component 3 Correlated with Product Strategies, Item of Component 4 Correlated with Promotion Strategies; Item of Component 5 Correlated highly with again with Sustainable Business Performance predictor. Whether this assumption is justified is another matter, but it is often done by those using the predictor investigation techniques. The major types of rotation oblique are generally employed

when you have some prior information that the predictor of Component item may be correlated and all components Item are equally loaded and those five components of the matrix have highly loaded.

9. TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

Table -5: Total Variance Explained

Table 5. Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.924	32.825	32.825	4.924	32.825	32.825	2.740	18.267	18.267
2	1.714	11.428	44.253	1.714	11.428	44.253	2.563	17.089	35.357
3	1.491	9.939	54.192	1.491	9.939	54.192	2.041	13.604	48.961
4	1.136	7.507	65.699	1.136	7.507	65.699	1.911	12.738	65.699
5	.852	5.679	67.378						
6	.694	4.629	72.007						
7	.685	4.569	76.577						
8	.579	3.863	80.439						
9	.536	3.576	84.015						
10	.472	3.148	87.163						
11	.441	2.938	90.101						
12	.423	2.820	92.920						
13	.392	2.614	95.534						
14	.341	2.276	97.810						
15	.328	2.190	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Source: SPSS output, (2022)

In Total Variance Explained, those 5 factors which have been found in exploratory factor analysis now have shown with eigenvalues results shown more than one based on this assumptions the factor analyses that produced with eigenvalues just above that, which reflects 61.699 percent of its total variance, with about 1.136 of its eigenvalues and eigenvalues possible rules which may be used for choosing the number of factor based on eigenvalues rule of greater than 1.0 it seem to work the best to Business Performance in ECX.

Scree Plot

Fig -3: Scree plot component number

Source: SPSS Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) Output (2022)

The present scree plot output result which corresponded Eigenvalues Eighteen Measurement construct separated only four measurement construct higher than 1.0 measurement construct value has to be returned. An elbow towards a less step observation scree plot and curve of declined value higher than 1.0 eigenvalues of doubt should be arise Four factors has to be returned and based on this reason the scree plot separation has to be accepted.

Plot Matrix Rotated Space

Fig -4: Plot Matrix Rotated Space

Source: Plot Matrix Rotated Space

Oblique rotation direct relation direct rotated in the axis such that the vertices can have some angle of 90 degree and allows predictors to be correlated one can be specify the parameter delta to control the extent to which predictors can be zero or negative, with number yielding nearly orthogonal solution five times a majority orthogonal rotated on his axis based on this reason the exploratory predictor analyses in the components of plot in rotated space is very well and as the result was supported by previous studies like (Chege Wang M., 2020).

10. CONSTRUCT VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY INVESTIGATION

Table -6: Reliability and validity of the measurement variables

Item	Construct	Cronbac h Alpha	KMO	Communalities	Factor converge Loading	AVE %
	Marketing Mix Strategies					
	Product Strategy	.724	.821			.553
PRO1	Product Strategy 1			.688	.743	
PRO2	Product Strategy 2			.725	.802	

PRO3	Product Strategy 3			.608	.581	
	Price Strategy	.747	.841			.529
PR11	Price Strategy 1			.571	.658	
PR12	Price Strategy 2			.673	.639	
PR13	Price Strategy 3			.561	.735	
	Promotion Strategy	.817	.832			.520
PRM1	Promotion Strategy 1			.673	.771	
PRM2	Promotion Strategy 2			.640	.783	
PRM3	Promotion Strategy 3			.655	.719	
	Place Strategy	.783	.782			.661
PLC1	Place Strategy 1			.734	.831	
PLC2	Place Strategy 2			.638	.723	
PLC3	Place Strategy 3			.611	.693	
PLC4	Place Strategy 4			.620	.753	
	Bu. Performance	.832	.861			.605
SMP 1	S. M. Profitability 1			.586	.712	
SMP 2	S. M. Profitability 2			.648	.764	
SMP 3	S. M. Profitability 3			.677	.751	
SMP 4	S.M. Profitability 4			.619	.634	

SMP 5	S.M. Profitability 5			.651	.639	
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Source: SPSS output, (2022)

It Construct the internal consistency of convergent Validity and Discriminant reliability extracted common factors have factor loading varying from 0.581 to 0. 771 which show that they are well above the critical value of 0.70, the construct reliability level assessed based alpha value highest value of alpha test .831 that it shows, the high measurement instrument reliability level. KMO index are varying 0.861 value result, which are either equal or AVE% Value above 0.50, depicted sufficient and sampling adequacy overall Communalities is more than 0.5 and the result for further reduced of variables in the proposed model to using SPSS v.22 used to Construct Validity and Discriminant Reliability investigation fit this model highly accepted.

II. CONCLUSIONS

Correlation matrix table that display the correlation coefficients for different variables that depicts correlation between all the possible pairs of value, it is a powerful tools to summarize large data set to identify all visualize pattern in data set, it can be seen at all the variables are positively correlated necessitating the significance arrow 1 diagonal number is more than 0.3 the variables after delated correlation Value of Product Strategy .680, Price Strategy .702, Place Strategy .668 Place Strategy .790 in the field of correlation coefficient as justified for the use of Exploratory factor analyzing hypotheses tests to be acceptable and positive significant correlation matrix in this study.

Predicator investigation is appropriate for this information and the sphericity calculates (Bartlett test) the potential of the association among enablers and as of these information, the test of Bartlett is considerable .844, which is associated as Chi-Square 2405.541,the Degree of freedom .153 probabilities is less than 0.05. Test of Bartlett for information is .000 and this shows the significance maximum fit well to the predicator investigation.

The Communalities information investigation observed communality is the squared correlation with its own ordinary proportion which has to be the proportion of variance that is explaiied by the ordinary predicators. In other sense the communality is the square of predicators, whereas greater communality more than .50 explains maximum measuring predicator which the related indicator all are fitted, but communalities of information were calculated PLACEI indicators which had highest predicator loading .734 with each predicator too, as stated in squared of predicator loading.

Item of Component 1 Place Strategies correlated each other, Item of Component 2 Correlated with Price Strategies, Item of Component 3 Correlated with Product Strategies, Item of Component 4 Correlated with Promotion Strategies; Item of Component 5 Correlated highly with again with Sustainable Business Performance predicator. Whether this assumption is justified is another matter, but it is often done by those using the predicator investigation techniques. The major types of rotation oblique are generally employed when you have some prior information that the predicator of Component item may be correlated and all components Item are equally loaded and five components of the matrix have highly loaded.

In Total Variance Explained, those five factors which have been found in exploratory factor analysis now have shown with eigenvalues results shown more than one based on this assumptions the factor analyses that produced with eigenvalues just above that, which reflects 61.699 percent of its total variance, with about 1.136 of its eigenvalues and eigenvalues possible rules which may be used for choosing the number of factor based on eigenvalues rule of greater than 1.0 it seem to work the best to sustain Business Performance in ECX.

The present scree plot output result which corresponded Eigenvalues Eighteen Measurement construct separated only four measurement construct higher than 1.0 measurement construct value has to be returned. An elbow towards a less step observation scree plot and curve of declined value higher than 1.0 eigenvalues of doabout should be arise Four factors has to be returned and based on this reason the scree plot separation has to be accepted.

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12. SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This research was limited to only Factor that affecting Marketing Mix Strategies on Sustainable Business Performance in Ethiopian Commodity Exchange that actively implemented in Ethiopian Commodity Commercialization system that sustain and upgrade like a system of coffee of Maize, Haricot bean, Dairy, Oilseeds and pulse for sustainable Market Performance, Business Performance, Export Performance, Market Participation, and Market Efficiency. Hence, it did not include other commodities other than Maize, Haricot bean, Oilseeds and pulse have focused only on those selected factors from Market Performance and Export Performance, Market Participation, and Market Efficiency or the supply side and to assess factor influencing Environmental Factor that affect Coffee Quality like Attitude, Amount of Rain fall, Availability of light, Temperature and Weather Condition has assessed. Therefore, it would be better for future study on Marketing and to develop Export Performance to be included and the effect of infrastructure/rural feeder Road, Warehouse, Information, Traditional Production System, Price discovery from Harvest to Export and Marketing mix strategies and Elements, by other influential variables which could affect marketing Mix strategies of ECX have a potential areas to develop the step economy of Ethiopia for further study.

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